

Ayurvedic management of *Sheetpitta* with special reference to Urticaria: A Case Study.

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Abstract

Ayurvedic therapies and practices have been integrated in universal wellness. Changes in lifestyle with development are very drastic. Diseased environment, junk food habits, work in shift duties, anxiety etc. are the main causative factors for vitiation of *Tridosha* and the demonstration of diseases in today's era. There is dearth of information about *Dincharya* and *Ritucharya* in common people. Due to which people mainly get aggravated doshas related to their gastrointestinal system first, and then other symptoms come subsequently. According to Ayurveda *Sheetpitta* is described as *Tridoshaj Vyadhi* (Disease), but Vata and Pitta Dosha are predominant and Ras and Rakta are main Dushya. *Sheetpitta* is one among the *Twak Vikara* (skin disorders) that have related Hetu of Kotha and Udarda. Vata and Kapha are two "Doshas", which are primarily bothered which in turn is associated through Pitta resulting in *Tridosha Prakopa* causing to redness, swelling itching on the skin etc. Chief symptoms of *Sheetpitta* are reddish spots, inflammation on skin with moderate to severe itching at site. It is compared with urticaria in modern science and termed as primary cutaneous disorder. An episode of it may start with pruritis. Episodes of urticaria may continue to revert for days, weeks, months or year if not cured properly. Urticaria is calculated as allergic reaction due to certain food and have only symptomatic treatment and anti-allergic drug. Commonly antihistaminic medicines were used for urticaria. In Ayurveda, treatment of *Sheetpitta* includes *Shodhana* and *Shamana Chikitsa*. Here we discussed about a case study of *Sheetpitta*. where we give Ayurvedic treatment and results were found very encouraging.

Keywords: *Sheetpitta*; Shaman; *Shodhan*; Urticaria; *Virechan*; Allergic reaction

1. Introduction

Sheetpitta is formed with two words which are exactly opposite to each other by their meaning. Here Sheet denotes Kapha and Vata and their combination with Pitta Dosha. In Ayurveda, *Sheetpitta* is mentioned as *Tridoshaj Vyadhi*, but Vata and Pitta Doshas are predominant and Ras and Rakta are main Dushya. Symptoms of allergic skin reaction described as Kotha in Brihatrayi, are later on Madhavkara developed as separate disease under the title *Sheetpitta-Udarda-Kotha*^[1]. *Sheetpitta* manifests due to exposure to contact with various poisonous materials (allergens) and intake of *Asatmya-Ahar-vihar*.^[2] Though it is not a life threatening condition but it cosmetically and extremely affects the quality of life. In Samhita causes given for *Sheetpitta* are *Lavana Katu Rasa*, *Shukta*, *Arnal*, *Sarshapa Atisevana*, Exposure to cold environment, wind, water, *Diwaswap*, *Asamyaka Vamana*, *Keeta Dansha*, *Krumi Sansarga*. When person comes in contact with above causes or similar to these causes Dosha gets vitiated. Further vitiated Dosha, leads to Ras and Rakta-dhatu Strotodusti, then it spreads towards the extremities and manifests as wheal/maculopapular rash^[3] and *Varati Damsha Sansthana Shotha* (urticaria), *Kandu Toda*, *Vidaha* are common symptoms associated with *Jwara* and *Chhardi* in few patients. All above features that closely mimics with urticaria. Urticaria is a dermal vascular reaction of the skin characterized by the appearance of itchy wheals, which are elevated (edematous), pale or erythematous, transient and evanescent plaque lesions^[4]. Modern pathology suggests that almost one third of Urticaria are cholinergic. It occurs either due to exercise, warming, anxiety or sweating. Elevated body temperature plays key role in

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pathogenesis. If urticaria persists less than 6 weeks duration is called acute urticaria while more than 6 weeks as chronic urticaria. Main causes include autoimmune reaction, allergens in food, inhalants and injections, drugs, contact (e.g. animal, saliva, latex), physical (e.g. heat, cold, water, sun, pressure), infection (e.g. viral hepatitis, infectious mononucleosis, HIV), idiopathic [5]. An episode of it may start with itching followed by red elevated patches at site of itching. Scratching, beverages, emotional conditions and exercise are provocative factors for the symptoms. Episodes of urticaria may continue to relapse for days, weeks, months or year, if not treated properly. Frequent attacks may hamper patient's mental condition. There is no permanently cure of Urticaria in modern science and treatment aims on Symptomatically. Repeated intake of anti-histamine or corticosteroids provide temporary relief as well as tend to reduce immunity threshold. Thus Ayurveda has important role in providing a comprehensive solution to this skin problem. Both the Shodhana (removing Doshas from the body by means of relevant Panchakarma) and Shaman (subsiding Doshas with proper internal medicine) treatment modalities are mentioned in Ayurvedic classics. In Bahudosh Avastha of any disease, Shodhana Chikitsa gives better results with minimum chances of recurrence. Considering this, the predominance Rakta, Pitta, Vaat Dosha, Virechan was followed by other medications were planned. Therefore, Virechana is very effective for the treatment of Sheetpitta.[6]

Aim and objectives

- To study the effect of Ayurvedic treatment (Shaman) in Sheetpitta.
- To study the effect of Mridu Shodhan (mild purgation) in Sheetpitta.

2. Case report

History of Present Illness- This is a case report of 28-year-old male patient complaining of reddish rashes all over the body with severe itching aggravating in early morning since 4-5months.

2.1. Personal History

Irregular bowel habit, liking of junk foods, late onset of sleep at night, excessive use of air conditioner (due to this temperature variations takes place), Patient was taking modern medicines for 4 months and was not satisfy with treatment. Due to Sheetpitta, he had to face lot of disturbance in his personal & social life, then he decided to consult at OPD.

Patient was diagnosed as chronic (Jirna) case of Sheetpitta.

History of Past Illness- Nil

Family History- Nil

2.2. Clinical Features

- Varati Damsha Sansthana Shotha: +++
- Kandu: +++
- Toda: +++
- Vidaha: +++
- Jwara: +++ (occasional)
- Chardi: +++ (occasional)
- (+ - Mild; ++ - Moderate; +++ - Severe)

2.3. General Examination

Pulse -72/min.,

BP -122/80 mm of hg

- Agni -Mandagni
- Koshtha -Asamyak
- Prakruti -Pitta Pradhan Kapha Anubandhi

2.4. Management

It has two Parts

- Shaman,
- Mridu Shodhan

2.4.1. Shaman Chikitsa

- Cows Ghee 1tsf + Maricha ¼ tsf (empty stomach at morning)
- Tab. Laghusutshekhar Rasa- 1tab. x bd (with lukewarm water)
- Shankha Bhasma - 500mg
 - Kamdudha Ras - 250mg Mukta Pishti - 250mg
 - Sheetpitta Bhanjan Rasa- 250mg 1 bd with Gulkand
 - Made a combination of all drugs as mentioned above and give to the patient in equal quantity in a form of small packets.
- Syrup Argleam forte (3tsf x bd after meal)
- Haridrakhand (1 tsf x bd with milk)
- Eladi tailam for local application

2.4.2. Mridu Shodhan Chikitsa (Mild purgation)

- Dipan & Pachan- Chitrakadi Vati -250 mg bd for 2 days
- Snehan- Tiktak Ghrita- 10 mg,20 mg,30 mg for 1 st , 2 nd and 3rd day accordingly
- Virechan – Trivrutta Avleha -20gm with milk (empty stomach at morning)

2.5. Do's & Don'ts

- Avoid sour, salty & spicy food, fast food, junk food.
- Curd, pickle
- Excessive travelling
- Uses of A.C.
- Wear full sleeves clothe.
- Avoid Humid weather
- Late night sleeping habit.

3. Result

Patient was instructed for follow up every 7 days. All the sign and symptoms before treatment is likely to diminished after Shodhan by Virecan and rest of Doshas are pacified by Shaman Chikitsa. At last follow up all symptoms i.e. Varati Damsha Sansthana Shotha (urticaria), Kandu (Itching), Toda (Pain), Vidaha (Burning), Jwara (Fever) and Chardi (Vomiting) were present in very soft state. Symptoms were not regular like before. Symptoms were going on and rotten, Previous studies have also shown that Sheetpitta can be cured well by Ayurvedic treatment. Diagnosis of Vyadhi Avastha and Nidan Parivarjan was the chief factor behind relief.

4. Discussion

In Sheetpitta there was vitiation of Kapha and Vaat due to *Shita-Amla Ahara* and Shita vihara. Kapha was dominant and Pitta was Anubandhi. In such condition Strotavarodha created by vitiated Kapha should be broken first. Charaka has advised drugs belonging to *Udarda Prashamana Mahakashya. Ushna-Tikshna-Laghu Guna*, Katu-Tikta Rasa helped to normalize vitiated Kapha and helped to remove the *Strotavarodha*, also at the same time Pitta achieved normal state after removal of Avarodha and in this *Laghusutshekhar* Ras was helpful to give relief in symptoms, same as Maricha has its active principle called piperine, and it has anti-inflammatory & antifungal effect so it works good on *Sheetpitta*. Clinically effects of urticaria are due to local vasodilatation causes redness, increase blood flow causes warmth, enhanced vascular permeability leads to swelling/edema, these are the feature of lewi's triple response. The main content of Haridrakhand is Haridra, which is a potent anti-allergic drug, recommended in various allergic conditions like urticaria. *Chitrakadi Vati* contains Piper nigrum, Piper longum and *Plumbago zeylanica* as chief major ingredients, which stimulates gastric fire. Roots of Chitraka (*Plumbago zeylanica*) are greatest appetite stimulant (Deepana), digestive (Pachana).^[7] Therefore, it helps in digestion of Ghrita and checks unto wards events due to digestion during

Snehapana. So Chitrakadi Vati was given before management of Ghrita.^[8] For the purpose of Snehapana (Internal Oleation), Tiktaka Ghrita was chosen to verify Pitta, also Vata & Kapha Dosha. It was suggested that the drugs present in the Ghrita may have some resemblance towards the target organ (Skin).^[9] Snehapana by desirable quality of its vitiating character of Dosha, it separates toxins and vitiating Dosha out of the body and helps to carry Doshas from Shakha (periphery of the body) to Koshta (center of the body i.e. to the intestines) later which will be debarred out of the body by the Virechana.^[10] Turpethin an active chemical constituent, present in Operculina Turpenthum is mainly responsible for purgative action. Therefore, it removes poisonous matter from body.^[11] It also has anti-inflammatory properties.

5. Conclusion

In *Sheetpitta*, there is Kapha and Pitta dominance, Ushna-Tikshna Gunatmak Kalpa like Laghusutshekhar Ras can be helpful. Virechan Karma (purgation) beside with Shaman (palliative) action is proved to be very effective in providing liberation in *Sheetpitta*. If disease is treated by breaking down of Doshas and Nidan Parivarjanam can absolutely get good results.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there was no conflict of interest regarding the publication of manuscript.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was taken from the patient.

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